

ONOMASIOLOGY AS A SCIENCE

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Annotation

The following article explored the branch of Onomasiology in linguistics. It compares Uzbek and English onomasiology, their types and analyzes. Types of analyzing onomasiology expressed with the vital examples including toponyms, proper nouns, etnonyms and other branches.

Key words: onomasiology, linguistics, toponyms, gidronyms, proper nouns, research of toponyms historically, historical- etymologic dictionary of toponyms, toponymic classification.

Lexicology is the study of words, and onomasiology is a branch of it. The goal in onomasiology is to find the linguistic forms or the words, that can stand for a given concept and idea or object. Like many words denoting sciences, the word onomasiology derived from two ancient greek words – “onoma” which means “name”, and “logos”, which can be translated as the “science” or “study of”. “Onomasiology” could thus be rendered as the “study of designations”.

Onomasiology closely connected to semasiology. Both these branches of linguistics deal with the relationships between words, reproduction, and reality. While onomasiology starts from concept, semasiology starts from forms and asks their meanings. Semasiology (derived from the Greek ancient words “semasia”, which means “to signify or name” and “logos “ is “science” or study”) is concerned with meaning and the change of meaning. A typical semasiological question is “Which meaning does this word have?”. For instance “Which meaning does the word *glass* have?”. a semasiological perspective is more the perspective of a listener who

is looking for the meaning of a word¹. Onomasiology and semasiology must go hand in hand in research about the changing relation between words and concepts. We could say that onomasiology and semasiology approach the same problem from different sides.

In Uzbek onomasiology Uzbek linguistics sphere was enlarged in the last century of 60- years. And there appeared separate branches of traditional grammar, lexicology and semasiology. Also, in this period, there was one new and developing branch of linguistics. It was Onomasiology.

It is clear that there was interest in the names from history. There are a lot of important and interesting facts in the ancient writing about the names of people, the meaning of places, ethnographics, meaning and etymology. But compiling materials and resources of onomastics systematically and in sequence, and analyzing scientifically began in Uzbek linguistics from 1960. We can see the initial research on onomasiology in the works of famous Uzbek scholars H.Hasanov, T.Nafasov, E.Begmatov. In the following years the branches toponymy, etnomy, antroponymy of onomasiology were developed by scholars. Nowadays we can note that the materials and recourse of Uzbek onomasiology are compiled and analyzed, the toponyms of regions of Uzbekistan are explored².

The research works on onomasiology caused development, improvement and prospering of this branch. The last years a lot of onomastic dissertations, research works, monographs has been defended and announced. And we can say that it is the result of developing of onomastic sphere in Uzbek linguistics.

After independence of Uzbekistan every branches of science are paid attention by the authority. The old and Uzbek traditional names, toponyms, etnonyms and other branches of onomasiology were appreciated and explored as the cultural heritage. As a result the directions of research has been expanded.

¹ Joachim Grzega and Marion Schoner English and general historical lexicology. Katcholic University, Germany, July 2007

² “Onomastika va toponimika fanidan ma’ruza matnlari” O’zbekiston Respublikasi xalq ta’limi vazirligi Aljiniyoz nomidagi Nukus davlat pedagogika universiteti ; Nukus 2012

Types of analyzing onomasiology. There are three types of analyzing onomasiology:

1. Terms which are based on theoretical onomasiology: scientific toponyms, onomastic directions, research of onomasiology, principals of setting up ancient names, ancient –etymologic directions, methodology of toponyms, general toponyms.

2. Scientific directions of proper nouns: names of ethnographs, onomastic lexicography, toponymic atlas, toponym of lexicography, to research toponyms, research of toponyms historically, historical- etymologic dictionary of toponyms, etymologic dictionary of toponyms, etymologic research of toponyms.

3. Methods of scientific research: toponymic classification //onomastic definition, toponymic classification // toponymic definition, to identify toponymic layer, chronological type, extralinguistic classification.

English belongs to the group of Germanic languages. English goes back to the same proto-language that is also the “mother” of Dutch, Low German, High German, Norwegian, Danish, Swedish, Icelandic. The group of Germanic languages, in turn, belongs to the Indo-European language family, like the Romanic languages and their “mother” Latin, the Celtic languages, the Balto-Slavic languages and others. Every word has a history, every word has an origin, every word has a motivated origin – even if the origin might no longer be transparent due to phonetic changes.

The concept of Naming Unit plays an important role in linguistic theories and is crucial for a functional, onomasiological approach to language and for the empirical study of word-formation, for semantics and pragmatics. The most famous scholars who investigated on this Naming unit are considered Mathesius, Stekaur, Grzega and others³.

In English language onomasiology was already initiated in the late 19th

³LIPKA Leonhard.2002, Names, onomasiology and semantics. In S.Scholz, Munchen: Langenscheidet-Longman, pp 217

century, but it did not receive its names until 1902, when the Austrian linguist Adolf Zauner published his study body-part terminology in Romance languages. And it is in Romance linguistics that the most important onomasiological works were written. But after that, it was introduced into linguistics by Vilem Mathesius in 1961. However his ideas were only published in English in 1975 in a book edited by J.Vachek, translated by L.Duskova, under the title “*A functional analysis of present day English*”.

English onomasiology has started within the field of lexicology, but could also be extended to grammar and pragmatics. And, actually, some linguists do so.

In every speech community there is the phenomenon of linguistic criticism. This often includes discussion on the benefit and the danger of foreign terms. In historical onomasiology one might be able to solve myths, for instance that an elevated degree of borrowings result in the decay of a language. We now know that borrowing is a natural lexical process in every language and does not threaten a language at all. In fact, we may ask whether it is not rather novelty of a word and not a foreignness of the word that causes negative emotions.

Onomasiology can also be help in other fields of the educational system. Due to knowledge of phonetic and semantic changes, it can acquiring English words more easy to learners with mother tongues related to English. They are able to show students that the change of designations does not change the thing. This can be relevant in understanding sociopolitical rhetorics and marketing language.

Further historical onomasiology can help to warn of historically insensitive neologisms. On the other hand, historical onomasiology can illustrate that interpreting a word only in its historical sense might equally well lead to an historically insensitive view.

References:

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